

EFFECTS OF SPECIFIC TRAINING AND INTELLECTUAL IMAGINARY TRAINING ON AGILITY OF INTER COLLEGIATE MALE BASKETBALL PLAYERS

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Cite This Article: Dr. V. Ravikumar, “Effects of Specific Training and Intellectual Imaginary Training on Agility of Inter Collegiate Male Basketball Players”, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 5, Issue 2, Page Number 47-50, 2019.

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Abstract:

Purpose of this study was to discover the impacts of specific training and intellectual Imaginary Training on agility of inter collegiate level Basketball players. To conduct the study, sixty male inter collegiate basketball players were chosen from G.S. College of Physical Education and they were divided into 3 equal groups. Group –I having specific training (n=20), Group –II having Intellectual Imaginary Training w (n=20) and Group –III was control group (n=20). The purpose of the study was to find out the agility of the players through shuttle run test as in standard mode. In the six-week of training period, the subjects in each group were trained 5 days in every week and control aggregate subjects were not given in any training. The collected data were analyzed by t ratio, analysis of variance, analysis of co-variance and Scheffe’s post hoc test. The results showed that the trainings caused for the significant ($P < 0.05$) improvement in the variable of agility. However, the specific training exhibited significant improvement in agility. Meanwhile Shuttle run training performance showed significantly greater improvement among the other 2 groups (intellectual imaginary training and control group). This study provided that the specific training has improved the agility.

Key Words: Specific Training, Intellectual Imaginary Training, Agility.

Introduction:

Sports offer numerous prospects for people to exhibit their abilities. It enhances the teamwork effort, enjoying the experience of joyfulness, sometimes the misery of losing also. In ancient times, our ancestors exhibited their extraordinary talents in terms of physical activity accompanied by aggressive competition. The arena of sports and games have developed professional dimension of human beings irrespective of age and sex. In this present world, the competition is involved in different kinds of sports either in recreation or professional. Sports becoming extremely competitive, it is not mere participation or practice but it makes an individual victorious. Specific Sports Training with Perceptual Skill practice and qualitative sports life is develops performance. Various factors like physiological adaptability, biomechanics, Modern sports training, sports medicine, sociological adjustments and coaching technique, computer application and psychology helps to achieve top level performance in the international arena. Regular fitness regimen and systematic execution is indispensable to improve performances. To win medals in the Olympics, there should be spotting of talent is plays a major role, besides the systematic and scientific method of training, competitive exposure, etc to be inculcated. Experts and stalwarts in the field of sports have put their attention and execute tremendous efforts to find out various ways to achieve top level performance.

Methodology:

To achieve this study, 60 men students with the age group of 18-25 were enrolled from G.S college of Physical Education, Coimbatore as subjects. They were randomly divided in to three equal groups of 20 subjects each and they were assigned as experimental group-I, experimental group-II, and control group. The experimental group-I underwent specific training, Experimental group-II underwent Intellectual Imaginary training and Group III was the Control group and not given any specific training. The student’s agility was found out through shuttle run test as existing method before the training. After the six-week of specific training period, the subjects in each group have gone for post training shuttle run test and data were collected. The collected data before and after training were analyzed by t ratio, Analysis of variance, Analysis of co-variance and Scheffe’s Post hoc test to find out the overall significant among the three groups.

Result and Discussion of the Study:

Table 1: Mean differences between Pre and Post Test of Specific Training Group on Agility of Inter Collegiate Basketball Players

Variables	Test	Mean	Std. Div.	S.E.M	M.D	‘t’ Ratio
Agility	Pre-Test	12.14	0.75	0.18	1.15	6.20*
	Post-Test	10.99	0.74			

Table 1 shows the obtained t' ratio (6.20) for pretest and Posttest mean difference of the selected variable. The obtained "t" ratio is higher than the table value of 2.09 with the degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of confidence (1, 19) and it was proved statistically significant.

Table 2: Mean Differences between Pre Test and Post Test of Intellectual Imaginary Training Group on Agility of Inter Collegiate Basketball Players

Variables	Test	Mean	Std. Div.	S.E.M	M.D	't' Ratio
Agility	Pre-Test	12.12	0.6	0.5	0.65	3.27*
	Post-Test	11.47	2.32			

Table 2 shows the obtained t' ratio (3.27) of pretest and Posttest mean difference of the selected variable, The obtained 't' ratio is higher the table value of 2.09 with the degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of confidence (1, 19) and it was proved statistically significant.

Table 3: Mean differences between pretest and posttest of control group on agility of Inter collegiate basketball players

Variables	Test	Mean	Std. Div.	S.E.M	M.D	't' Ratio
Agility	Pre-Test	12.12	0.73	0.08	0.04	0.49
	Post-Test	12.07	0.68			

Table 3 shows the obtained t' ratio (0.49) of pretest and Posttest mean difference of the selected variable, The obtained 't' ratio is lesser than the table value of 2.09 with the degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of confidence (1, 19) and it was proved statistically not significant.

Table 4: The Table Shows the Mean Values of Pre Test, Post Test and Adjusted Post of STG, ITG and Control Group on Agility

Test	STG	ITG	CG	Source of variance	Sum of square	df	Mean square	'f'
Pre-Test	12.14	12.12	12.12	B.G	0.008	2	0.004	0.08
				W.G	28.07	57	0.49	
Post –Test	10.99	11.47	12.07	B.G	11.72	2	5.862	2.73*
				W.G	122.2	57	2.144	
Adjusted Post Test	10.98	11.48	12.08	B.G	12.04	2	6.022	2.99*
				W.G	110.5	55	2.009	

Table 4 reveals that obtained 'f' value of experimental group – I, experimental group – II and control group respectively. The obtained 'f' ratio 0.08 was lesser than the table value is 2.72 at 0.05 level of significance; hence the pre test value was not significant.

The obtained Post – test 'f' value 2.73 for experimental group – I, experimental group – II and control group, the obtained 'f' ratio 2.73 was higher than the table value 2.72 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the Post test value was significant and it was proved statistically significant.

The obtained Adjusted Post – test 'f' value for experimental group – I, experimental group – II and control group is 2.99, which was higher than the table value 2.72 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the Post test value was significant and it was proved statistically significant.

It was concluded that there was a significant mean difference among the specific Training Group and Intellectual imaginary Training Group in developing the Agility of Inter collegiate basketball players.

Table 5: The Scheffe's Test for the Differences between Pared Means on Agility

STG	ITG	CG	Mean Differences	C.I
11.48	12.08	-	0.6	1.271
11.48	-	8.7	-2.78	1.271
-	12.08	8.7	-3.38	1.271

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence

Table 5 shows the post hoc analysis of obtained adjusted post test means. The confidential interval mean difference required to be significant was 1.27. It was observed that the mean difference values of specific training group in developing the Agility was significantly higher than the Intellectual Imaginary training group and control group. Intellectual Imaginary training group developed the Agility better than the control group.

Agility:

The specific training group, Intellectual Imaginary training significantly showed improvement in Agility from pre test to post test. The Agility increased in the STG group from pre test (12.14 ± 0.75) to post test (10.99 ± 0.74); ITG group from pre test (12.12 ± 0.60) to post test (11.47 ± 2.32); and there were no change in control group from pre test (12.12 ± 0.73) to post test (12.07 ± 0.68). The Agility significantly showed improvement from pre test to post test in the two Treatment groups and there was no changes in control group.

The present study demonstrated that an increase in Agility of 9.47 %, 5.36% and 0.33 % was estimated with the specific training group, Intellectual Imaginary training and control group respectively. The specific training group significantly showed improvement in Agility by 9.47 % better than the Intellectual Imaginary training group 5.36 % and control group 0.33 %. The Intellectual Imaginary training improved in Agility by 5.36% better than the control group 0.33 %.

Result of the Study:

- It was resulted that the Specific training significantly improved the Agility of the Inter collegiate male basketball players.
- It was resulted that the intellectual imaginary training significantly improved the Agility of the Inter collegiate male basketball players.
- It was resulted that the intellectual imaginary training significantly improved the Agility better than the control group of the Inter collegiate male basketball players.
- It was resulted that the specific training, intellectual imaginary training significantly improved the Agility better than the control group of the Inter collegiate male basketball players.

Conclusion:

- It was concluded that the intellectual Imaginary training significantly developed the Agility of inter collegiate male basketball players.
- It was concluded that the specific training is the paramount training to develop the Agility of inter collegiate male basketball players. It showed significantly improved better than the intellectual Imaginary training and control group.

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